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*There Is a World Beyond The Stars Too*****

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REGIONAL DISPARITIES IN LITERACY IN HIMACHAL PRADESH AMONG SCHEDULED CASTE AND NON-SCHEDULED CASTE POPULATION: 2001

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Introduction

Indian society is composed of different social groups, among which scheduled caste and tribals are dominant. In India, there are a number of such social groups, which constitute a considerable portion of population. These include former untouchables or scheduled caste, tribal, nomadic, semi-nomadic and de-notified tribes which together constitute more than one-fourth of total population (Thorat and Mahamallik, 2005). These groups have historically suffered in the past from exclusion in multiple spheres, which has led to their severe deprivations. The scheduled tribes are less discriminated as compared to scheduled caste population in India. While scheduled caste belongs to the lowest hierarchy of social order and is often considered impure or unclean, the scheduled tribes have, for the most part, been socially and spatially distanced and living outside the mainstream of Hindu society (Mitra and Singh, 2007).

The term 'scheduled caste' appeared for the first time in the Government of India Act, 1935. The scheduled castes are specified in accordance with Article 341 of the Indian Constitution. The schedule caste (SC) constitutes the largest social group in India accounted for about 17 percent (equivalent to 167 millions) of the total population in 2001. In the case of lower caste untouchables, the exclusion resulted in severe deprivations and poverty since they were historically denied access to all sources of livelihood-from access to property rights, education and civil rights (Thorat, and Mahamallik, 2005). Against such a backdrop, scheduled castes remained behind than the mainstream throughout the country.

Literacy Among Scheduled Caste

Educational disparities contribute a great deal in generating large inequalities in the Indian society largely derived from more fundamental inequalities such as those of class, caste and gender (Dreze, 2003). Literacy among scheduled caste has ever remained lower than the general population. In 2001, literacy among scheduled castes has registered 54.69 percent literacy rate against 64.82 percent in total population and 66.76 percent in non-scheduled caste population. Mizoram with 89.02 percent literacy among scheduled castes was on the top whereas Bihar with 28.47 percent literacy was at the bottom of all states with a difference of 60.55 percent between highly literate and least literate state in India.

Himachal Pradesh scored fifth position in the general literacy rate in the country, but, it could not keep the same rank in case of literacy in scheduled caste population. With a literacy rate of 70.31 percent in schedule caste population state has 8th position among all states. Mizoram (89.02 percent), Kerala (82.66 percent), Tripura (74.68 percent), Manipur (72.32 percent), Goa (71.92

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percent), Maharashtra (71.90 percent) and Gujarat (70.50 percent) states have higher literacy rate among scheduled castes than Himachal Pradesh.

In Himachal Pradesh, Hamirpur district has the highest literacy rate of 79.15 percent in scheduled caste population against 83.49 percent in non-scheduled caste population. Chamba district on the other end, has registered lowest literacy rate among both, scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste population which is 56.65 percent and 61.62 percent respectively. The study reveals that the difference between literacy rate of scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste population is almost similar on both ends. Kullu (64.90 percent), Mandi (68.58 percent) and Sirmaur District (63.57 percent) are other districts displaying literacy below than the state average (table 2).

Table 1 reveals that literacy in male scheduled caste population is 80.01 percent as compared to 60.35 percent in female scheduled caste population in Himachal Pradesh. Hamirpur and Chamba district registered highest (86.36 percent) and lowest (71.44 percent) male literacy respectively against 72.24 percent and 45.04 percent among female scheduled caste population. Average male-female disparity index in literacy among scheduled caste is 0.188 in Himachal Pradesh. It is highest in Chamba (0.281) and lowest in Hamirpur district (0.128).

The variation in literacy of scheduled caste population is not a corollary of low literacy in the adult population but is also a product of low literacy in young population. Chamba district with lowest literacy rate has 87.13 percent literacy rate in 7-14 age group. Same time age group above 30 years did not register literacy more than 50 percent in least literate Chamba district. On other hand, Hamirpur district experienced literacy rate of 97.47 in 7-14 age group and at least half of scheduled castes are literate up to 50 years age groups. Kinnaur and Lahul-Spiti District are also experiencing high level of literacy.

State as a whole registered 70.31 percent literacy but there are wide variations in literacy rates all over the state. Though, variations in literacy at district level are significant but at the lower administrative i.e tehsil level these become more discernible and are much sharper. Shimla urban tehsil with 84.58 percent literacy is on the top among all the tehsils whereas Shalai, with 46.07 percent scheduled caste population as literate, is at the tail end. Apart from these contrasts, there are spatial disparities in literacy at different levels of the spatial scale.

Table - 1

Himachal Pradesh Male-Female Literacy and Gender Disparity 2001 (Data by Districts)

District	Non-Scheduled Caste (% literacy)	Scheduled Caste (% literacy)	Difference In % Points	Disparity Index Value
Chamba	64.00	58.47	5.53	0.0565
Kangra	81.61	74.21	7.39	0.0676
Lahul & Spiti	72.86	75.99	-3.13	-0.0291
Kullu	75.97	64.90	11.07	0.1055
Mandi	77.89	68.58	9.31	0.0872
Hamirpur	83.49	79.15	4.34	0.0391
Una	81.64	75.90	5.74	0.0522
Bilaspur	79.39	72.95	6.44	0.0593
Solan	78.72	70.98	7.74	0.0718
Sirmaur	73.17	63.57	9.60	0.0927
Shimla	82.01	70.72	11.28	0.1040
Kinnaur	75.53	72.08	3.45	0.0322
HIMACHAL PRADESH	78.46	70.31	8.15	0.0758

* Source: Census of India, 2001

In Himachal Pradesh as a whole, pattern of scheduled caste literacy mirrors the pattern of general literacy. An overall analysis reveals that there are wide spatial variations in the attainment of the literacy. The highest rates of literacy are marked by semi-hilly areas of Kangra, Una, Hamirpur and Bilaspur; Solan and Shimla district and in northern part in tribal belt partaking Lahul-Spiti and Kinnaur district. The reasons for such high literacy in the semi-hilly region of the state are economic engagement of people in armed forces, tradition of out-migration to larger cities and inclusion of many backward classes in the scheduled caste category and multifunctional nature of their work. In predominantly tribal areas, the literacy rates among the scheduled castes are higher.

The lowest rates of literacy are characteristics of areas in the central part of the state. These are the areas where scheduled caste population is overwhelmingly associated with farming and allied activities, where general resource base is poor and overall development is lacking even among the general population. The very low literacy among female scheduled caste population is another reason for the overall low level of literacy.

The spatial pattern of moderately literate population, in many cases, represents a transition between the two main categories of high and low literacy, depending upon the relative location of the concerned area.

Disparity In Literacy Among Scheduled Caste And Non-Scheduled Caste Population

According to 2001 census, while only 70.31 per cent of scheduled caste population is literate, the corresponding figure for the non-scheduled caste population was 78.46 percent, resulting into disparity index of 0.0758. The high disparity in literacy between non-scheduled caste and scheduled caste population is result of severe deprivations and denials; low level of social interaction; association with menial occupation; prevalence of abject poverty; high percentage of child and female participation in domestic labour; backlog of mass illiteracy and low level of socio-economic awakening (Sagar, 1990).

The index of disparity varies from one district to another. It is found lowest in Lahul-Spiti (-0.0291) and highest in Kullu district (0.1055). Negative index value in Lahul-Spiti district is a product of high scheduled caste literacy than scheduled tribes and non-scheduled caste population. The high index value in Kullu district is due to relatively high literacy among non-scheduled caste population and more rigid caste system and prevalent socio-economic segregation which resulted into low scheduled caste literacy.

Table 2
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District	Non-Scheduled Caste (% literacy)	Scheduled Caste (% literacy)	Difference In % Points	Disparity Index Value
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* Source: Census of India, 2001

Spatial Patterns

In view of diverse physical setup, socio-cultural and historical background, the index of literacy disparity between non-scheduled caste and scheduled castes could not be expected to be uniform in the state. There is an inverse correlation between index value and literacy among scheduled caste population (-0.501).

Areas with Low Disparity Index

Entire northern belt including most of areas of Chamba, Lahul-Spiti and Kinnaur district; western part partaking Kangra, Una, Hamirpur, and Bilaspur district are making a contiguous belt covering more than one third of total tehsils and more than half of the total state area. The areas with low disparity index are largely confined to western and northern part of the state. There are some scattered tehsils apart from contiguous belt. Low disparity in literacy is not only experienced in areas with high scheduled caste literacy, but, also in areas where scheduled caste literacy is also low.

In all, there are 44 such tehsils in which index value is less than 0.060. Out of the 44 tehsils in this category of low disparity, 4 tehsils have registered negative disparity index, where scheduled caste population has high literacy level than non-scheduled caste population. Other 20 tehsils are experiencing disparity index even less than 0.040 and most of these are interestingly located in the notified tribal areas of state which include Pangti and Bharmaur blocks of Chamba, Lahul-Spiti and Kinnaur District.

In Lahul & Spiti district, Lahul and Udaipur tehsils are experiencing negative disparity index. In these tehsils, non-scheduled caste population consists of mainly scheduled tribes and some general population comprising labourers and employees. Even Scheduled tribes do not have low

literacy level but maximum of scheduled tribe educated population has taken out-migration for jobs and education. In case of scheduled caste population such out migration is comparatively low. The out migration of educated scheduled tribe population is also high in Kinnaur district which makes scheduled castes relatively high or equally literate to the non-scheduled caste category.

In Chamba district, the low disparity is a result of very low level of literacy in both non-scheduled caste and scheduled caste population. None of tehsil has literacy among non-scheduled caste population even more than the state average of scheduled caste population (70.31 percent). Thus, low disparity in literacy among non-scheduled caste and scheduled caste population in these tehsils is due to overall low level of literacy in all sections of the society.

The above described belt marked with low disparity index, is followed in continuity by parts of Kangra, Hamirpur, Una, Bilaspur and Mandi districts experiencing high literacy in general population and among scheduled castes as well. Moreover in this part of the state, the caste system is not much rigid as compared to other parts of the state. There has been no discrimination for acquiring education on the caste basis since long times. Easy access and early start of education also motivated scheduled castes to acquire education. Relatively more out-migration of educated non-scheduled caste population than the scheduled caste educated population is also the feature of this area. The entire belt except few tehsils has registered high literacy among scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste population. Khundian in Kangra district, Haroli in Una district are exceptions in this regard where literacy level is found moderate among scheduled caste.

Lastly, there are some scattered tehsils, like Nahan in Sirmaur district, Kotkhai in Shimla, Ani in Kullu and Kandaghat in Shimla district displaying low level of disparity in literacy among non-scheduled caste and scheduled caste population. Except Ani, all these tehsils have shown high literacy rate both among scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste population.

In nutshell, the low disparity index is not following any type of physical barriers and representing a combination of literacy level between both groups. In other words, either high or low literacy level between two sections is resulting into low index value.

Areas with High Disparity Index

There are 39 tehsils recording an index value of more than 0.080. Out of these, 26 tehsils registered index value of 0.100 and above, implying a very high degree of disparity in the literacy rates of the two sections. The areas of high disparity are also confined to the areas experiencing low and high level literacy in scheduled caste population. However, these areas are in majority where scheduled caste population is experiencing low level of literacy. It also forms a continuous belt of high disparity in literacy covering most of central part and further towards southern part of the state. There are two other small pockets in same category observed in Kangra and Chamba district. None of tehsil in Una, Hamirpur, Bilaspur, Lahul-Spiti and Kinnaur district is experiencing high disparity index.

The belt representing high disparity index in the central part of state, covering parts of Mandi and Kullu district, has very low literacy among scheduled castes. Most of tehsils except Mandi and Bilaspur have large gap in literacy among both sections. The relatively low literacy among scheduled caste population can be attributed to engagement of scheduled castes particularly *Dhogris* in lumbering, found in Mandi district. In Kullu district, the caste system has remained so rigid up to recent past which resulted into large base of illiterate scheduled caste population.

Map - 1

Himachal Pradesh
 Scheduled Caste Literate as Per Cent of
 Total Scheduled Caste Population
 2001
 (Data by Tehsil)

No. of Tehsil	Percent Population
10	78
39	72
21	66
21	60
18	60

State Average 70.31%

Map - 2

Himachal Pradesh
**Disparity in Literacy in Non-Scheduled Caste
 and Scheduled Caste Population**
 2001
 (Data by Tehsil)

No. of
Tehsils

Disparity
Index

- 26
- 13
- 26
- 24
- 20

State Average 0.076

In continuity of this belt, 9 tehsils in Shimla district are also showing high disparity index. Among these tehsils only Chirgaon, Dodra Kwar and Cheta have less than 70 percent literacy among non-scheduled caste, and literacy rate among scheduled castes is also very low in these tehsils i.e. 50.53 percent, 48.59 percent and 51.09 percent respectively resulting into high disparity index. Among other tehsils of Shimla district, experiencing high disparity in literacy have low literacy among scheduled castes. In Shimla district the rigidity of caste system is also prominent. In Sirmaur district, 8 tehsils are also the part of contiguous belt of high disparity index i.e. more than 0.080. Interestingly, all tehsils of Sirmaur district in this category are representing very high index value i.e. more than 0.100. In Sirmaur district, the general pattern of literacy increases from east to west and same pattern is followed in case of scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste population. The general trend of decrease in literacy from west towards east is mainly due to availability of resources and their utilization; connectivity with other parts of the state and recent introduction of education both among scheduled castes and non-scheduled castes decreasing from west to east. The decrease in literacy level has resulted into increase in disparity index (Fig. 2).

Solan (0.096), Krishangarh (0.095) and Nalagarh (0.094) tehsils in Solan district further continue with the same belt of high disparity. Despite high level of urbanization in Solan tehsil, it has registered high disparity in literacy among non-scheduled caste and scheduled caste population. Though scheduled caste population has significantly high (77.61 percent) literacy level but is relatively low as compared with non-scheduled caste population (88.35 percent). It is due to high concentration of scheduled caste population in rural areas. Both the remaining tehsils, Krishangarh and Nalagarh have recorded 62.63 percent and 69.17 percent scheduled caste literacy respectively which is less than state average against non-scheduled caste literacy of 72.34 percent and 79.41 percent respectively. Scheduled castes of these tehsils are primarily engaged in primary activities (Fig. 2).

Apart from continuous belt covering 34 tehsils there are two small pockets in Chamba and Kangra district marked by high disparity index. In Saluni and Bhalai tehsils of Chamba district there is very low literacy observed in scheduled caste population and non-scheduled caste population. Other tehsils are experiencing high literacy both among non-scheduled caste and moderate literacy in scheduled caste population. Dharamshala has however high literacy among scheduled castes (72.33 percent) but it is far behind than non-scheduled caste population (82.75). These tehsils of Kangra district are dominated by *Sippi* caste which has low level of literacy (56.60 percent). Thus, the areas with high disparity index between scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste population are found in high and low literacy areas. However high disparity is more or less associated with areas where scheduled caste population has low literacy and non-scheduled caste has moderate to high level of literacy. These areas are also characterized by remoteness, rigid caste system or sometimes amalgamation of both.

Areas with Moderate Disparity Index

There are 26 tehsils where disparity index is within the range of 0.060 and 0.080 index value. Moderate disparity index in literacy is recorded in parts of Shimla, Solan, Kangra and Mandi districts whereas Una, Bilaspur, Kullu, Kinnaur and Sirmaur districts have one tehsil each found with moderate literacy rate. All these tehsils have moderate to high level of literacy in both sections of society. It is more evident from the fact that the literacy level among scheduled castes is 65 percent

and non-scheduled castes 70 percent barring Ramsahar tehsils in Solan district witnessing low literacy rate.

The main pocket of moderate literacy consists of 7 tehsils of Shimla, 3 of Solan, and 1 each of Mandi and Bilaspur districts. In general literacy pattern, this belt is one of the high literacy belts. These are areas where non-scheduled caste literacy is very high due to early start of education, good economic conditions and growing urban centers. The literacy among scheduled caste is also high but relatively lower than non-scheduled caste population. The study reveals that 7 tehsils in Kangra district, 2 tehsils in Una district are also displaying moderate index of disparity in literacy. These areas also represent high level of literacy among non-scheduled caste population but literacy among scheduled caste is relatively low which contributes in narrowing down the disparity gap between two sections.

Fig. 2 illustrates that Nichar (0.061) in Kinnaur district, Paonta Sahib (0.062) in Sirmaur district and Manali (0.073) in Kullu district have registered moderate disparity index. These three tehsils are laying in the areas of high and low disparity index hence acting as areas with transition. The study therefore indicates that areas with moderate disparity index are mainly experiencing high level of literacy among non-scheduled caste population and had relatively moderate to high literacy level. Moderate disparity index is also found in areas juxtaposed between high and low index value. Areas under moderate literacy level are relatively well developed but scheduled caste population has yet to make inroads in this regard.

Concluding Remarks

It is evident from foregoing discussion that with 70.31 percent of literate population, the scheduled castes are still lagging behind from the mainstream society in terms of literacy development despite the promotional and protective provisions. The study reveals that the literacy scenario of scheduled caste population has witnessed remarkable improvement however, it still follows the pattern of general literacy in Himachal Pradesh. The high literacy level is associated with economic engagement of people in armed forces, tradition of out-migration to larger cities and growing urbanization and its impact on surrounding rural areas. It is also noted that the factors responsible for high literacy among scheduled castes are almost same as in case of general literacy. The areas with low level of literacy are areas where either caste system is very rigid, scheduled caste population is largely engaged in primary activities or suffer from inaccessibility. Areas of moderate literacy among scheduled castes are commonly those where general population literacy level is high. These areas also dot the landscape under transition influence of both high and low literacy level, where impact of both side factors is clearly discernible on the literacy level.

✓ The study explores that the literacy gap between the scheduled castes and non-scheduled castes is still high which is responsible for wider inequity in the literacy level between both sections of the society. It is evident from the fact that the sectional disparity index in literacy is about 0.076. Such disparity is a corollary of long and intermittent administrative changes and complex caste system. Spatially, there is a close correspondence between the patterns of disparity index and scheduled caste literacy. Low disparity index is however found in all three types of areas of scheduled caste literacy i.e. high, middle or low. High disparity in literacy is associated with those

areas where majority of tehsils have registered low level of literacy among scheduled castes. Moderate disparity in literacy is observed in parts recording high literacy in scheduled caste population.✓✓

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